

Sample 06a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0016
	{Fe}	34.1
	{Si}	17.8
	{Ca}	13.6
	{Si, Ca HiP}	5.8
	{Al, Si}	3.8
	{Al, Ca}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	3.4
	{Ca, Fe}	2.8
	{S, Ca}	2.3
	{Si, Fe}	1.2
	{Mg, Fe}	1.2
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.1
	{Mg, Si}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.9
	{Al}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.6
	{S}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.4
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Al, Si, K}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Cl}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.1
	{Al, Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{S, Fe}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.1
Pellet	1.5
Ore preparation undifferentiated	20.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.9
BOF converter slag	6.6
BOF converter slag slopping	1.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	2.1
Desulph slag	0.3
Ca-aluminate slag	2.5
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.2
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	2.1
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	8.4
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	13.4
Carbon rich - other	9.3
Cement or BOF converter	0.9
Cement	0.1
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.3
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	7.5
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.1
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.3

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	34.0
Site - ore / hot metal	1.9
Site - slag	12.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	2.1
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	8.4
Site - carbon-rich other	13.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	9.3
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.9
Urban	0.5
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	7.5
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.3

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 06b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0007
{Fe}	34.6
{Si}	19.0
{Ca}	13.6
{Si, Ca HiP}	7.2
{Al, Si}	3.4
{Si, Ca LoP}	3.2
{Ca, Fe}	3.2
{Al, Ca}	2.4
{S, Ca}	1.9
{Mg, Fe}	1.5
{Si, Fe}	1.3
{Si, S, Ca}	1.0
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
{Mg}	0.7
{Mg, Ca}	0.6
{Mg, Si}	0.6
{Al}	0.6
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Na, Si}	0.4
{Na, Al, Si}	0.4
{Al, Si, K}	0.3
{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Mg, S, Ca}	0.2
{S}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
{Si, K}	0.1
{Na, Si, Ca}	0.1
{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Mn}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{Al, Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Ti}	0.1
{Si, P, Ca}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.9
Pellet	1.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	17.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.1
BOF converter slag	9.9
BOF converter slag slopping	0.8
Slag BOF converter or desulph	1.0
Desulph slag	0.1
Ca-aluminate slag	0.9
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.1
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	7.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	14.5
Carbon rich - other	11.5
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	7.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.2
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.8

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	31.6
Site - ore / hot metal	2.1
Site - slag	12.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.1
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	7.3
Site - carbon-rich other	14.5
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	11.5
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	0.1
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	7.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.2
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.8

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 06c

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0031
	{Fe}	31.5
	{Si}	21.7
	{Ca}	11.8
	{Si, Ca HiP}	5.6
	{Al, Si}	4.3
	{Ca, Fe}	3.6
	{Si, Ca LoP}	2.8
	{Al, Ca}	2.6
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.8
	{S, Ca}	1.7
	{Si, Fe}	1.5
	{Al, Si, K}	1.2
	{Mg, Fe}	1.1
	{Mg, Ca}	1.0
	{Si, S, Ca}	1.0
	{Al}	0.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.7
	{Mg}	0.6
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.5
	{Mg, Si}	0.5
	{Mg, Al}	0.4
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Mg, S, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mn}	0.2
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.1
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Fe}	0.1
	{S, Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Al, S, Ca}	0.1
	{S}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	12.8
Pellet	1.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	17.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	2.9
BOF converter slag	9.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.7
Desulph slag	0.8
Ca-aluminate slag	1.8
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	1.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.7
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.2
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.2
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.3
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	11.3
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	8.4
Carbon rich - other	6.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.7
Cement	0.2
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.1
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.1
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	14.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	6.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.7

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	32.1
Site - ore / hot metal	2.9
Site - slag	12.7
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.7
Site - flux / refractory	0.2
Site - refractory	0.2
Site - scrap	0.3
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	11.3
Site - carbon-rich other	8.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	6.9
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.7
Urban	0.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	14.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	6.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.7

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels